

Enhancing School Literacy through Multicultural Islamic Education: An Evidence From a Mining School

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 25, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: July 26, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Multicultural Islamic Education, School Literacy Movement, Active Reading, Inclusive Character</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8185110</p>	<p><i>This research investigates the implementation of the School Literacy Movement (SLM) in instilling multicultural Islamic education values at miningschool. The research methodology used a qualitative approach through observation, interviews, and document analysis. The collected data will be analyzed to identify the multicultural Islamic education values and how these values are implemented in the SLM program. The research findings demonstrate that through SLM activities such as loud reading, book creation, art showcases, book discussions, and book writing, the school has successfully created a learning environment that encourages active reading and the development of inclusive character. The findings contribute to interactive literacy teaching, integrating popular culture, applying digital literacy approaches, and implementing local wisdom values in learning.</i></p>

Introduction

This study identifies Indonesia's low reading habits and literacy levels, as revealed in previous research. Marmoah et al., Wahab and Amaliyah, and Wangid, Mustadi, and Putri are among the researchers who have addressed this phenomenon (Marmoah et al., 2022; Wahab & Amaliyah, 2021; Wangid et al., 2018). The UNESCO survey conducted in 2011 ranked Indonesia at the lowest position with a score of 0.001, indicating that only one out of approximately 1000 Indonesian citizens has a high reading culture (Silvia & Djuanda, 2017). Additionally, the PIRLS survey in 2011 and PISA in 2018 also showed that the literacy achievement of Indonesian students still needs to improve compared to other countries (Marmoah et al., 2022).

This condition is also evident in Jakarta, where literacy practices focus only on school-based literacy celebrations without comprehensive efforts from the government, schools, and the community. However, in countries like Taiwan, it has been proven that multilingual literacy programs can encourage literacy habits early and achieve high rankings in reading and mathematics literacy, according to the PISA 2018 report (Mayuni et al., 2020).

To address the low reading habits and interest in reading in Indonesia, the government has launched the School Literacy Movement through the Ministry of Education and Culture. This movement aims to enhance students' reading abilities and comprehension through programs such as 15-minute reading sessions, Friday Qur'an recitation, and school libraries (Minsih et al., 2020). In its implementation, effective and facilitative management of school literacy programs involving all school components is crucial (Lastiningsih et al., 2019).

Several previous studies have examined the implementation of literacy education and its management system in improving students' abilities. Auberry investigated the influence of literacy education on students' abilities (Auberry, 2018), while Maulida and Suriansyah explored the management of literacy culture in elementary schools and found that schools with good literacy culture management systems tend to achieve better outcomes than those that do not implement such programs (Maulida & Suriansyah, 2019). Additionally, aspects of planning, organization, habituation, and control in implementing literacy programs have also been studied (Marmoah et al., 2022).

Various studies have been conducted to understand related aspects in the context of literacy teaching and learning. These include the use of popular culture in literacy curricula (Marsh, 1999), interactive teaching by primary school teachers in the National Literacy Strategy in England (Hargreaves et al., 2003), literacy dimensions in teaching and learning (Hall et al., 2010; Kucer, 2009), as well as energy, visual, and multilingual literacy in teaching and learning (Alper et al., 2017; DeWaters et al., 2013; Ntelioglou et al., 2014). Studies have also focused on the use of technology in kindergarten literacy curricula (Turbill, 2001), scientific and information communication technology (ICT) literacy at various school levels (Detlor et al., 2011; Fives et al.,

2014; Kim et al., 2014), as well as emotional and mental health literacy (Bjørnsen et al., 2019; Ibrahim et al., 2019; Liao et al., 2003).

In multicultural Islamic education the approach to multicultural Islamic education in Indonesia can promote overall multicultural education (Normuslim, 2021). Studies on multicultural education in Bali have shown that multicultural education influences the formation of tolerance among Islamic high school students (Ainna et al., 2019). Furthermore, multicultural education also supports creating an inclusive Islamic community in the Pamekasan Regency (Sahibudin et al., 2020). Outside of Indonesia, Islamic religious education in Spain has also been proven to prevent and counter religious radicalization (Rodríguez García, 2019). However, Muslim schools in Canada face unique challenges in negotiating between preserving Islamic values and the social-political pressure to integrate into a multicultural society (Ali & Bagley, 2015).

The influence of Islam on moral values within a multicultural society must be considered to ensure effective moral education (Balakrishnan, 2017; Sismanto et al., 2022). Islamic ethics align with intercultural empathy and multicultural education (El-Atwani, 2015). The transformation of character has an impact on diverse students' values (Sismanto, 2023). Educational animations based on Islamic religion and local culture can be a preventive measure against religious radicalism (Malla et al., 2020). Developing a multicultural education curriculum in a pesantren aims to build students' understanding of multicultural values and appreciation for diversity in life (Maarif & Arifin, 2022; Maslani, 2012; Muhajir et al., 2020).

Based on the context of this research, it is important to explore the values of multicultural Islamic education within the framework of the School Literacy Movement. The approach of multicultural Islamic education, which includes the formation of an inclusive character, the development of a culture of respect, and the recognition of human dignity in diversity (Baidhawiy, 2005; Hasan, 2016; Ma'arif, 2019). Can contribute to the development of reading habits within the School Literacy Movement. Multicultural Islamic education teaches the importance of respecting and acknowledging diversity as part of the identity of others (Cikusin, 2016). Therefore, this study aims to identify how multicultural Islamic education can serve as the foundation for developing reading habits within the School Literacy Movement. Additionally, this research will examine the management of school literacy programs involving all school components and supportive and facilitative management behaviours.

This study is expected to provide a better understanding of implementing multicultural Islamic education values within the School Literacy Movement. Through a deeper understanding of multicultural Islamic education, solutions can be found to enhance reading habits and literacy in Indonesia. Furthermore, this research aims to improve the overall quality of education by creating an inclusive, diverse, and high-quality educational environment.

Method

This research utilizes a qualitative approach to understand the implementation of multicultural Islamic education values in the school literacy movement. The qualitative approach allows researchers to explore and understand the complex context and obtain rich perspectives on the research participants' experiences, beliefs, and attitudes (Creswell, 2007).

The research was conducted at YPPSB Elementary School, a school located in a coal mining company in Indonesia. The selection of this school was based on the consideration of exploring the implementation of multicultural Islamic education values in the school literacy movement within an industrial mining context. It is expected to provide specific and unique insights regarding the factors influencing school literacy.

The data collection methods used in this research include observations, interviews, and document analysis (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016; Yin, 2014). In data analysis, the approach used involves data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion. The collected data will be reduced through coding and categorization to identify patterns, themes, and important concepts. The reduced data will be presented using tables, diagrams, or direct quotations. Subsequently, the presented findings will be analyzed to identify relevant patterns, trends, and relationships (Miles et al., 2014).

Results and Discussion

Result

Based on the research, various Islamic educational values found at the research site are Love, Scholar, and Leadership. The school literacy movement is based on the concept that children can read texts and understand and integrate messages, enabling them to adapt to their environment. With sufficient literacy skills, students can develop themselves and process the information they acquire, allowing them to interact effectively in a diverse society. The research results are presented in the following table:

Table 1 *The implementation of multicultural Islamic educational values through the school literacy movement program*

No	Theme	Activities
1	Program Socialization	The program is conveyed to parents, students, other institutions and communities
2	15-Minute Loud Reading Movement	Students and the management/teachers/staff members between units conduct it before the first period every day.
3	Corner Formation	Reading It includes establishing reading corners, providing reading materials, procuring bookshelves, creating stand banners and billboards, and developing Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for organizing reading corners.
4	Story Implementation	Sharing It is done in the morning before teaching and learning activities for 2-3 minutes
5	Competency Enhancement of Team	It includes benchmarking visits to schools/institutions that have implemented SLM and the implementation of an SLM workshop
6	CIKAL (Love for Local Wisdom) Movement and Development Trends	It involves writing competitions, book/article writing, collaboration with publishers, cultural study competitions and appreciation, and career introduction through culminating thematic activities.

Based on the data above, the research findings include the following activities implemented in YPPSB Sangatta: 1) Program socialization to parents and students (internal), 2) Program socialization to other institutions and communities, 3) 15-minute oral reading movement before the first class every day, 4) 15-minute oral reading movement by management, administrators, and teachers/staff between units twice a week, 5) Establishing communities, 6) Collaborating with similar communities.

Meanwhile, the establishment of reading corners in YPPSB School is carried out through the following steps:

1. Provision of reading corners for teachers/staff and students
2. Provision of reading materials (fiction books, newspapers, magazines, bulletins) for teachers, staff, and parents
3. Bookshelf procurement
4. Creation of stand banners and billboards
5. Development of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for organizing the reading corner

The internal program socialization to parents and students is conducted at the beginning of each academic year by the school principal, vice principals, and homeroom teachers of YPPSB School. In the 2022/2023 academic year, the program was reintroduced to teachers and parents, and a meeting was held with the management of YPPSB. Furthermore, the program was also socialized to other institutions and communities in February 2023. The socialization was conducted by Prima Baca and the YPPSB Publication team through the following mechanisms: 1) The program was delivered by the school literacy movement (SLM) team to the library team, and 2) Information was disseminated through social media.

The 15-minute oral reading movement before the first class every day started in February 2023, beginning Semester 2 (2023). According to the YPPSB director's decree, a school literacy team comprised of the school principal, vice principals, homeroom teachers, and Indonesian language teachers responsible for implementing this activity. The implementation of the 15-minute oral reading movement before the first class was scheduled three times a week, with the exact time adjusted and controlled by the class teacher/homeroom teacher using a report book. The 15-minute oral reading movement between units by management, administrators, and teachers/staff was conducted twice a week. In the early days of the second semester of the 2022/2023 academic year, the activity started with socialization to the management and the creation of a schedule. However, in practice, the 15-minute oral reading movement between units by management, administrators, and teachers/staff only occurred once a month.

YPPSB School conducts Story Sharing activities in the morning before the teaching and learning activities start, lasting 2 to 3 minutes. In addition, the integration of sharing activities that are personally or book-based, both individually and in groups, takes place in various forums such as group play and class and is integrated with national/religious commemoration days, providing opportunities for students to share their learning/reading experiences in the classroom.

YPPSB Sangatta also enhances the competency of the School Literacy Movement (SLM) team through the following approaches: 1) Study visits to schools/institutions that have implemented the SLM, and 2) SLM workshops. The school's documents related to the literacy movement reveal the CIKAL (Love for Local Wisdom) movement and trends in science and technology (IPTEK) as follows:

1. Writing competition for all school members conducted once a year, from July to October, coinciding with the YPPSB School's anniversary.
2. Writing other books/works at least once a year, with themes aligned with school activities
3. Collaboration with publishers

In 2023, YPPSB School coordinated with the logistics department of YPPSB for administrative completeness and cooperation; 4) Cultural study competition and appreciation for students and parents. The implementation takes place in October - November and is integrated into the Language Month activities; 5) Introduction to professions through theme highlights, Empowerment of potentials (with alums and employees).

Based on the above data, the implementation of the school literacy movement in YPPSB Sangatta is carried out through read-aloud activities, including program socialization to parents and students (internal), program socialization to other institutions and communities, 15-minute oral reading movement before the first class every day, 15-minute oral reading movement by management, administrators, and teachers/staff between units, establishing communities, and collaborating with similar communities. Establishing reading corners in YPPSB School involves providing reading corners, reading materials, bookshelves, stand banners, and billboards and developing Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for organizing the reading corner.

Multicultural Islamic Education

Based on the research findings conducted in the field, the values of multicultural Islamic education developed in SD YPPSB include love, intellectuality, and leadership. The school's reasons for developing these values of multicultural Islamic education include: (1) upholding religious values and traditions, (2) embracing the paradigm of education for all, (3) implementing the values of love for God and love for others, (4) awareness and appreciation of diversity, and (5) preparing students for a multicultural society. The following diagram can summarize the findings from the field research:

Based on the field data findings, several forms of multicultural Islamic education values have been implemented at SD YPPSB 3 Sangatta Utara. The research findings indicate that at SD YPPSB 3 Sangatta Utara, three main values encompass various sub-values of Multicultural Islamic Education. These values are love, intellectuality, and leadership. The school's literacy movement aims to develop students' reading and understanding abilities, enabling them to adapt to their environment and interact effectively in a diverse society.

The school's literacy movement is implemented through activities such as the 15-Minute Loud Reading Movement, establishing classroom reading corners, program socialization to parents, students, institutions, and other communities, and story-sharing and exchange activities. There is also an emphasis on enhancing the

competence of the GLS team through benchmarking visits and workshops. Additionally, there are initiatives such as writing competitions, book/article writing, collaboration with publishers, appreciation of cultural studies, and career awareness. The socialization of the school literacy program is conducted for parents, students, and school staff at the beginning of the academic year, as well as through institutions and other communities via teams and social media. The literacy movement is integrated with other activities, such as national/religious holiday celebrations and the development of local wisdom.

The research findings also reveal three main values at SD YPPSB Sangatta, encompassing various sub-values of multicultural Islamic education: love, intellectuality, and leadership. It is relevant to instilling love, intellectuality, and leadership values within the context of multicultural Islamic education at SD YPPSB. These values help students develop understanding and appreciation for cultural and religious diversity within the school environment. This data is in line with Hasan's view on inclusive Islamic character, involving elements such as ta'aruf (getting to know each other), tasamuh (tolerance), and ta'awun (collaboration)(Hasan, 2016, p. 60). The applied approach of multicultural Islamic education at SD YPPSB also includes the school's literacy movement, such as program socialization to parents and students, loud reading movements, the establishment of classroom reading corners, and collaborations with institutions and other communities.

In the context of multicultural education theory, Normuslim states that multicultural Islamic education can promote general multicultural education (Normuslim, 2021). In line with the SD YPPSB field findings, the approach of multicultural Islamic education has goals that go beyond religious aspects alone, emphasizing students' abilities to interact and adapt to a diverse environment. Moreover, empirical data also reveal that multicultural education influences the formation of tolerance attitudes among high school students in Islamic Schools in Bali(Ainna et al., 2019). These findings demonstrate that multicultural Islamic education can foster inclusive, tolerant, and enthusiastic attitudes in students towards learning cultural diversity. The multicultural education approach also supports establishing an inclusive Islamic community in Pamekasan Regency, as shown in Sahibudin et al.'s research. It confirms the relevance of the multicultural Islamic education approach in building an inclusive society that understands diversity within the context of Islam(Sahibudin et al., 2020).

In a global context, Ali and Bagley's research highlights the unique challenges faced by Muslim schools in Canada in navigating between maintaining Islamic values and societal-political pressures to integrate into a multicultural society. It emphasizes the importance of the multicultural Islamic education approach in navigating complex social and cultural realities(Ali & Bagley, 2015). From a moral values perspective, Balakrishnan emphasizes the need to consider the influence of Islam on moral values in a multicultural society to carry out moral education effectively(Balakrishnan, 2017). The approach of multicultural Islamic education at SD YPPSB also considers these aspects by implementing values of love and leadership in character development.

Furthermore, Malla et al.'s research highlights the importance of education-based Islamic animation media and local culture as preventive measures against religious radicalism(Malla et al., 2020). It indicates the potential use of media in supporting the approach of multicultural Islamic education in promoting positive values and preventing extremism. Developing a multicultural education curriculum in a pesantren aims to build students' understanding of multicultural values and appreciation for diversity in life(Maslani, 2012; Muhajir et al., 2020). These findings provide insights that multicultural Islamic education can be implemented in various educational contexts, including traditional Islamic institutions such as pesantren.

Based on the above discussions, the empirical data revealed in the research at SD YPPSB consistently support the importance of multicultural Islamic education in promoting comprehensive multicultural education. The data indicate that this approach can influence attitude formation, enrich moral values, foster multicultural understanding, and utilize media as an educational tool. Additionally, the data confirm the relevance of previously proposed multicultural education theories and demonstrate that multicultural Islamic education can be applied in various educational contexts in Indonesia and globally.

On the other hand, multicultural education values such as democracy, humanism, and pluralism should be an integral part of their teaching ethos. For example, teachers can encourage student participation and ensure that every voice in the classroom is heard and respected, reflecting democratic principles. They can also instil empathy and appreciation for the humanity of all individuals, aligning with humanistic principles. By applying the principle of pluralism, teachers can appreciate and encourage diversity regarding cultural backgrounds, opinions, or student learning styles. Thus, teachers can play a vital role in shaping an inclusive and tolerant school community through the literacy movement.

School Literacy Movement

Based on research findings on cultivating multicultural Islamic education values through the school literacy movement, this school has successfully created a learning environment that encourages students to actively read, understand messages, and develop inclusive and multicultural characters. Through the School Literacy Movement activities, students improve their reading and comprehension skills and better understand multicultural Islamic education values.

These research findings align with Christie's view that literacy involves reading, writing, and punctuation skills, which are also skills that teachers should possess (Christie, 2012). The implementation of the School Literacy Movement in YPPSB Sangatta School considers literacy aspects that involve students in reading, writing, speaking, and listening activities. The literacy movement focuses on reading and writing skills and understanding, analyzing, and interpreting information daily (Faizah et al., 2016).

This research also highlights efforts to enhance the school's digital literacy and literacy culture management. Marmoah et al. emphasize the importance of school literacy program management, which involves all components of the school and supportive management behaviour (Marmoah et al., 2022). In line with the research findings that indicate the implementation of the School Literacy Movement in YPPSB Sangatta School involves various activities such as loud reading, setting up reading corners, program socialization to parents and other institutions, and enhancing the competence of the School Literacy Movement team.

These findings can be related to previous research identifying Indonesia's low reading habits and literacy rates (Marmoah et al., 2022; Wahab & Amaliyah, 2021; Wangid et al., 2018). Additionally, the results of the PIRLS survey in 2011 and PISA in 2018 also indicate that Indonesian students' literacy achievements still need to be higher compared to other countries (Marmoah et al., 2022). These findings underline the need to improve students' reading abilities and reading interests in Indonesia.

In implementing the school literacy movement, the school adopts various activities involving students. For example, they conduct read-aloud sessions, where students read stories to their peers to teach positive values such as kindness, friendship, and cooperation. The school also encourages students to create books to express their creativity. The Primavaganza art showcase serves as a platform for students to showcase their artistic talents by highlighting themes of local culture and religious beliefs. In this art showcase, students can demonstrate their abilities in drama, music, dance, or choir while conveying positive messages related to the teachings of Islam.

Furthermore, book discussions and writing activities are also part of the school literacy movement. Through book discussions, students can share their understanding and perspectives on the multicultural Islamic education values found in the books they read. Book writing serves as a platform for students to express their thoughts and views on the importance of multiculturalism.

This research demonstrates that schools can become agents of change in developing a better literacy culture by implementing the school literacy movement and activities that actively involve students. Previous research findings also indicate that school literacy program management involving all components of the school and supportive management behaviour is an important factor in the success of literacy programs (Marmoah et al., 2022). These findings reinforce the understanding that collaboration among the government, schools, communities, and academics is crucial in improving the literacy culture in Indonesia.

Furthermore, the importance of digital literacy education is also highlighted in this research. Previous research findings show that digital literacy education positively impacts knowledge, understanding, and skills in using social media (Rina et al., 2020). Therefore, implementing digital literacy education in schools and communities can also enhance students' literacy and ability to use social media wisely. The research findings justify and support previous research results indicating the low literacy rates in Indonesia and the need for efforts to improve the literacy culture. Implementing the school literacy movement, managing school literacy programs, and providing digital literacy education are important steps in addressing these challenges and building a better literacy culture in Indonesia.

In conclusion, the research findings in this study conclude that the school literacy movement in YPPSB Sangatta School has successfully created a learning environment that supports the development of students' literacy and the cultivation of multicultural Islamic values. The school literacy movements activities, such as loud reading, book creation, art showcases, book discussions, and book writing, actively involve students in gaining an understanding of multicultural Islamic values. Implementing the school literacy movement in YPPSB has created an environment that supports the development of students' literacy and fosters an appreciation for differences, an understanding of religious and cultural diversity, and acceptance of values such as tolerance, respect, and cooperation.

Conclusion

Based on this research, implementing the School Literacy Movement (SLM) at YPPSB Sangatta School has successfully created a learning environment that supports the development of students' literacy and cultivates multicultural Islamic values. SLM activities, such as loud reading, book creation, art showcases, book discussions, and book writing, actively involve students in gaining an understanding of multicultural Islamic values.

This research also reaffirms that reading habits and literacy levels in Indonesia are still low, consistent with previous research findings. It highlights the importance of improving students' reading skills and interests in Indonesia. The management of school literacy programs involving all components of the school and supportive

management behaviour is also a crucial factor in the success of literacy programs. Additionally, the research findings highlight the importance of digital literacy education in addressing the current digital era. Implementing digital literacy education in schools and communities is important in enhancing students' understanding and skills in using social media wisely.

In the context of literacy teaching and learning, this research contributes by connecting the aspects of literacy instruction with previous theoretical studies. It emphasizes the importance of interactive literacy teaching, integrating popular culture, applying digital literacy approaches, and implementing local wisdom values in learning. Thus, this research provides a deeper understanding of the importance of the School Literacy Movement, the management of school literacy programs, digital literacy education, and literacy instruction in improving reading skills, reading interests, and the development of multicultural values among students in Indonesia. These findings serve as a basis for the government, schools, communities, and academics to develop strategies and programs to enhance the literacy culture in the country.

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